

Small Clonal

Scaffold 1

Small Clonal

Scaffold 2

Small Clonal

Scaffold 3

Small Clonal

Scaffold 4

Small Clonal

Scaffold 5

Big Clonal

Scaffold 1

Big Clonal

Scaffold 2

Big Clonal

Scaffold 3

Big Clonal

Scaffold 4

Big Clonal

Scaffold 5

French Clonal

Scaffold 1

French Clonal

Scaffold 2

French Clonal

Scaffold 3

French Clonal

Scaffold 4

French Clonal

Scaffold 5

Kenya

Scaffold 1

Kenya

Scaffold 2

Kenya

Scaffold 3

Kenya

Scaffold 4

Nucleotide diversity

fs1

fs2

fs3

fs4

fs5

fs6

fs7

fs8

fs9

fs10

fs11

fs12

fs13

Tajima's D

Kenya

Scaffold 5

Nucleotide diversity

fs1

fs2

fs3

fs4

fs5

fs6

fs7

fs8

fs9

fs10

fs11

fs12

fs13

Tajima's D